

Syntheses in the Triazine Series.

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Of the three possible types of triazines A, B, and C, type B seems to have been very little studied.

(A)

(B)

(C)

Few derivatives of this type (unsymmetrical α -triazine) are known. Besides none of the methods so far adopted for synthesising these simple rings is of wide applicability and almost all of them suffer from the disadvantage that the starting materials are difficult to obtain. In the present paper some unsymmetrical α -triazines have been synthesised and their properties studied. The synthesis was effected from such simple materials as hydrazines and acyl glycines in the manner of the syntheses of pyrazolones (Knorr, *Annalen*, 1887, 238, 137) and of pyrrodiazolones (Andreocci, *Gazzetta*, 1890, 19, 448) from hydrazines and β -ketoic esters and acyl urethanes respectively.

The method is expected to be one of wide applicability as by varying R, R', R'' and R''' a large number of triazines can be obtained.

The condensations were brought about by heating molecular proportions of the reactants in alcoholic solutions on the water-bath for 6 to 8 hours. Phenylhydrazine reacted smoothly with acetyl

phenylglycine, acetyl-*o*-tolylglycine and acetyl- α -naphthylglycine. The products are all insoluble in both dilute and concentrated alkali solutions showing that they have no acidic properties. Dilute acids too have no action. They dissolve, however, in concentrated hydrochloric acid but are precipitated unchanged on dilution with water. They are, therefore, very weak bases. With concentrated sulphuric acid they form bright rose-red solutions.

Efforts to synthesise these triazines from acyl hydrazines and glycines met with indifferent success.

Acetylphenylhydrazine (symmetrical) could not be made to react with either phenylglycine or its ethyl ester though a variety of ways were employed.

Acyl derivatives of unsubstituted glycines (hippuric acid and acetylglycine) were next made use of to note if a triazine or an iminazolone or a mixture of both would result, as in these cases there is the chance of the formation of both.

In both the cases the compounds obtained melted indifferently even after repeated fractionations from different solvents, that from hippuric acid melting between 178 and 186°, and that from acetyl glycine between 200 and 206°. The analytical results tallied closely, however, with those demanded by compounds obtainable from the reactants by elimination of two molecules of water. This showed clearly that in these two cases intimate mixtures of triazines and iminazolones were being formed. The presence of the iminazolones

has been proved indirectly by condensing hippuric acid with unsymmetrical phenylbenzyl hydrazine under identical conditions.

The expected iminazolone was obtained in good yield thus proving the full possibility of the formation of an iminazolone under these conditions.

All efforts at separation having failed attempts were next made to arrive at the triazines by way of the intermediate phenylhydrazones.

From phenylhydrazine and hippuric acid Scheiber and Reckleben (*Ber.*, 1913, **46**, 2419) had obtained hippuryl hydrazide $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ (m.p. 184°). Here hippuric acid was heated in aqueous solution with phenylhydrazine hydrochloride and sodium acetate when the desired intermediate phenylhydrazone (m.p. 134°) was formed, though in poor yield. It was soluble in alkalis, showing the presence of a carboxyl group. For ring-closure this was heated at a temperature a few degrees above its melting point. On crystallising however the same mixture of triazine and iminazolone with the same indifferent melting point was obtained. This shows that the hydrazidine skeleton is tautomeric like amidines. It was observed that on longer heating the final product was formed along with the intermediate phenylhydrazone from which it was separated by washing with alkali.

It may be noted here that with benzoyl glycines the yield was invariably greater than with acetyl glycines, thus indicating the influence of the phenyl group on the adjacent carbonyl group.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Acetylphenylglycine.—Phenylglycine was obtained by heating one molecule of monochloroacetic acid with two molecules of aniline and water on the water-bath for two hours (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, **87**,

438) and was acetylated by heating with acetic anhydride (*Ber.*, 1892, 25, 2270).

Condensation with Phenylhydrazine: Formation of 2:5-Diphenyl-6-methyl-3-ketotetrahydro- α -triazine. (Formula I, R = CH₃, R', R''' = Ph, R'' = H).—Acetylphenylglycine (3.6 g.) and phenylhydrazine (2 g.) were heated in alcoholic solution (30 c.c.) on the water-bath for seven hours. The alcohol was evaporated off and the resulting oily mass was triturated first with dilute hydrochloric acid when it became solid and then with dilute sodium carbonate solution. Finally it was washed with a little ether. On crystallising now twice from alcohol rectangular plates, m.p. 163-164°, were obtained. (yield, 2.6 g.) (Found: N, 15.91. C₁₆H₁₅ON₃ requires N, 15.85 per cent.).

The triazine is insoluble in dilute as also in concentrated alkali solution. Dilute hydrochloric acid is without any action. It dissolves in concentrated hydrochloric acid but is reprecipitated on diluting with water. With concentrated sulphuric acid it gives an immediate and permanent bright rose-red colour. It is soluble in ethyl and methyl alcohols, benzene, chloroform, acetone, glacial acetic acid and ethyl acetate and insoluble in ether and ligroin.

Acetyl o-Tolylglycine.—*o*-Tolylglycine was prepared in the same manner as phenylglycine and the acetylation was carried out by heating with acetic anhydride at 180° in an oil-bath. (*Ber.*, 1892, 25, 2270.)

2-Phenyl-5-o-tolyl-6-methyl-3-ketotetrahydro- α -triazine. (Formula I, (R = CH₃, R' = C₇H₇, R'' = H, R''' = Ph).—A solution of acetyl *o*-tolylglycine (5 g.) and phenylhydrazine (2.5 g.) in alcohol (40 c.c.) was refluxed for ten hours. The oily product obtained on removal of the solvent was washed successively with dilute hydrochloric acid and dilute sodium carbonate solution and finally crystallised from alcohol. Rectangular plates, m.p. 183-184°, were obtained (yield, 3.2 g.). (Found: N, 15.12. C₁₇H₁₇O₃ requires N, 15.05 per cent.).

Its behaviour towards acids and alkalis both dilute and concentrated resembles that of the previous compound.

Acetyl α -Naphthylglycine.— α -Naphthylglycine was obtained by heating α -naphthylamine and monochloroacetic acid with water on the sand-bath (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 2372). Treatment with acetyl chloride in the cold gave acetyl α -naphthylglycine (*Ber.*, 1892, 25, 2290).

2-Phenyl-5- α -naphthyl-6-methyl-3-ketotetrahydro- α -triazine. (Formula I, R = CH₃, R' = C₁₀H₇, R'' = H, R''' = Ph).—Acetyl

α -naphthylglycine (4.8 g.) and phenylhydrazine (2 g.) were heated in alcoholic solution (50 c.c.) on the water-bath for eight hours. The triazine was isolated after evaporating off the solvent and washing away the unacted upon reactants in the usual manner. Two crystallisations from alcohol gave fine scales, m.p. 221° (yield, 3.5 g.) (Found: N, 13.45. $C_{20}N_{17}ON_3$ requires N, 13.33 per cent.)

The triazine exhibited the same properties as the two previous compounds.

Condensation of Hippuric Acid with Phenylhydrazine.—An alcoholic solution of hippuric acid (5.4 g.) and phenylhydrazine (3.2 g.) was heated under reflux for five hours. The product was isolated as usual by removing the solvent and the unaltered reactants, and recrystallised; a sample having a sharp melting point could not be obtained even on repeated fractionations from different solvents (alcohol, acetone, and ethyl acetate). The final fractions like the first fractions melted between 178 and 186°. (Found: C, 71.56; H, 5.44; N, 16.83. $C_{15}H_{13}ON_3$ requires C, 71.71; H, 5.17; N, 16.73 per cent.)

The product is insoluble in dilute acids and in dilute or concentrated alkalis. It dissolves in concentrated hydrochloric acid but is precipitated unchanged on dilution with water. With concentrated sulphuric acid it forms a rose-red solution almost immediately. It is soluble, easily in alcohol, acetone and glacial acetic acid, appreciably in ethyl acetate and sparingly in benzene, chloroform, ether and ligroin.

Hippuric Acid Phenylhydrazone (VI).—An aqueous solution of phenylhydrazine hydrochloride (2.5 g. in 50 c.c.), sodium acetate (6 g.) and hippuric acid (3 g.) were heated on the water-bath for three hours. The phenylhydrazone separated out after some time and was crystallised from alcohol in fine scales, m.p. 137-138°. (Found: N, 15.67. $C_{15}H_{15}O_2N_3$ requires N, 15.61 per cent.)

The phenylhydrazone is soluble in alcohol, acetone and acetic acid and insoluble in benzene, chloroform and ether. It dissolves in alkalis and decomposes on keeping for some months.

Ring-closure.—The phenylhydrazone (2 g.) was heated at 155-160° for half an hour. On crystallising twice from alcohol in presence of animal charcoal rectangular plates, m.p. 177-186°, were obtained. The m.p. was not depressed by admixture with a sample obtained directly from hippuric acid and phenylhydrazine.

Acetylglycine was obtained by heating glycine with acetic anhydride in benzene solution on the water-bath (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 1664).

Condensation with Phenylhydrazine.—Acetyl glycine (4.7 g.) was condensed with phenylhydrazine (4.3 g.) in the usual way. The product on crystallisation from alcohol melted at 200-206° and no improvement was observed in the melting point on crystallisation and recrystallisation of the different fractions from either alcohol or acetone. (Found: N, 22.34. $C_{10}H_{11}ON_3$ requires N, 22.22 per cent.)

*Condensation of Hippuric Acid with
asym.-Phenylbenzylhydrazine.*

1-Phenylbenzylamine-2-phenyl-5-iminazolone (*Formula V*).—An alcoholic solution (40 c.c.) of hippuric acid (5 g.) and phenylbenzylhydrazine (5.5 g.) was refluxed on the water-bath for eight hours. The solvent was evaporated off and the viscous mass washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and dilute sodium carbonate solution. On crystallising from alcohol needles, m.p. 147°, were deposited (yield, 7 g.). (Found: N, 12.27. $C_{22}H_{19}ON_3$ requires N, 12.31 per cent.)

The iminazolone is insoluble in acids and alkalis both dilute and concentrated. With concentrated sulphuric acid a rose-red colour develops after a short time. It is soluble in alcohol, benzene, chloroform, acetone, acetic acid, and ethyl acetate and insoluble in ether and ligroin.

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